

PROFESSIONALISM, ADMINISTRATIVE SKILLS, AND COMMITMENT OF DANCESPORT TECHNICAL OFFICIALS

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Professionalism, Administrative Skills, and Commitment of Dancesport Technical Officials

Rosebelle S. Baldostamon*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

DanceSport is the new signature for competitive ballroom dancing, which was originally intended to reflect the sport's current reputation as a difficult one. Physical strength, agility, coordination, stamina, a high degree of fitness, discipline, teamwork, grace, style, and musical interpretation are among its attributes. In the past few decades, DanceSport has experienced tremendous expansion and development, garnering more public attention and remarkable breakthroughs on the professional front. Even with this growing acknowledgment, there is a conspicuous lack of scholarly writing on the responsibilities, proficiencies, and professionalism of DanceSport technical officials—important individuals in charge of guaranteeing the uniformity, impartiality, and general prosperity of contests. These officials are essential in maintaining the caliber and integrity of competitions, acting as the backbone of the sport. This descriptive-correlational study determined the professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment among DanceSport technical officials in Panay Island, Region VI, Philippines for the School Year 2023-2024. A researcher-made questionnaire on professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment was used. Majority of respondents were members of LGBTQ+, 31 to 40 years old, bachelor's degree holders with units toward master's degree, 11 to 20 years in service, and teaching personnel. The level of professionalism as a whole was very high. In terms of gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work, their level of professionalism was very high. The level of administrative skills as a whole was very high. In terms of gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work, their level of administrative skills was very high. The level of commitment as a whole was very high. In terms of gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work, their level of commitment was very high. There were no significant differences in the level of professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work. However, a significant relationship existed in the level of professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment. Based on the findings of the study on professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment among DanceSport technical officials, it is recommended that organizations develop specialized workshops focusing on these key areas to strengthen their capabilities. Additionally, establishing a mentorship program may help new officials quickly acquire the skills and knowledge necessary for high-level performance. Finally, implementing regular feedback and evaluation mechanisms will ensure ongoing improvement and maintain high standards within the DanceSport community.

Keywords: *professionalism, administrative skills, commitment, dancesport technical officials*

Introduction

DanceSport, often known as competitive dance, is a well-liked, widely-distributed activity in which participants dance in front of a panel of judges in any of the accepted dance forms, including tap, improve, hip-hop, lyrical, modern, jazz, acro, and ballet. Dancing is perilous, just like any other activity; dancers can sustain lifelong injuries. For this reason, dancing can also be considered a sport. Dancing competitions are open to both individuals and teams, to entertain both themselves and spectators (Quora Digest, 2022).

Professionalism is a key component of any professional field. It includes technical proficiency as well as interpersonal skills, ethical awareness, and adaptability in a constantly changing work environment (Garcia and Hernandez, 2020). Within the domain of DanceSport, referees must possess flawless judgment, objectivity, and a deep understanding of the complex technical elements associated with the dance styles they supervise. At the same time, administrative skills including efficient time management, tactical planning, and skillful communication become equally important for Technical Officials. These competencies serve as the foundation for the smooth operation of events, promoting effective teamwork and raising participant and stakeholder satisfaction levels (Thompson and Evans, 2020).

Considering the complex logistics and the diverse array of stakeholders in DanceSport, including dancers, event organizers, and audiences, the administrative adeptness of officials significantly contributes to the overall success of competitions. Another crucial element that is being investigated is commitment, which is often a factor in determining work quality, job satisfaction, and sustained engagement in a field. Higher levels of commitment from technical officials are likely to improve both the overall experience of competitors and the quality of contests (Roberts, 2020).

The researcher observed a notable research gap concerning the interplay between professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment among these officials. In addition, the specific dynamics within the niche domain of DanceSport technical officials are underexplored. This study aims to fill this gap by examining these dimensions through a descriptive correlational approach, thereby offering a comprehensive understanding of the roles and responsibilities of DanceSport technical officials.

Furthermore, the selected provinces for this study, including Iloilo, Aklan, Capiz, and Antique, represent diverse communities with varying degrees of involvement in DanceSport. By exploring this, the researcher understood how these officials perceive and enact professionalism, how their administrative skills influence competition management, and the factors contributing to their commitment could provide valuable insights.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the levels and the relationships among professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment of the DanceSport technical officials in Panay Island, Philippines for School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work?
2. What is the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole and when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work?
3. What is the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole and when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work?
4. What is the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials as a when taken as a whole and when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work?
5. Are there significant differences in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work?
6. Are there significant differences in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work?
7. Are there significant differences in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work?
8. Are there significant relationships among professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment of DanceSport technical officials?

Literature Review

On Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials

DanceSport is what used to be referred to as competitive Ballroom Dancing, renamed to suit its modern image as a demanding sport. Its characteristics consist of physical strength, agility, co-ordination, stamina, high level of fitness, discipline, teamwork, grace, style and musical interpretation.

DanceSports or Competitive dance is a popular, widespread sport in which competitors perform dances in any of several permitted dance styles—such as acro, ballet, contemporary, jazz, hip-hop, lyrical, modern, musical theatre, tap, and improve—before a common group of judges. The competitors compete by dancing and performing the style of their choice before a common group of judges. These judges give them points which provides rank to an individual performer or a team. Dance can also be classified as a sport because it is equally as dangerous as any other sport – dancers are prone to lifetime injuries. Both teams and individuals can compete in dance competitions for their own entertainment and the entertainment of spectators (Quora Digest, 2022).

Professionalism is a set of standards that an individual is expected to adhere to in a workplace, usually in order to appear serious, uniform, or respectful. What constitutes professionalism is hotly debated and varies from workplace to workplace and between cultures (Oxford Languages Dictionary, 2024).

Key values of professionalism include acting in the best interest of others and maintaining a certain standard and knowledge base expected of those in your specific profession. These certain standards include ethical elements such as integrity, honor, accountability, and responsibility, but also humanistic qualities such as caring, compassion, humility, and kindness. In addition, professionals need to have a social responsibility and sensitivity to other people's culture and beliefs. In the sporting world, professionalism is not just an individual's responsibility; it is part and parcel of the broader organizational culture. The level of professionalism exhibited by officials can significantly impact public perception of the sport. This lends weight to the importance of the current study, which aims to explore this complex and multi-layered construct in the context of DanceSport.

Professionalism in Dance Education is a complex construction. It can be imposed from the outside (by degree completed, job status, salary) or can be identified by the professional herself. The dance educator can achieve more than one level of professionalism in life, first as a dancer and then as a dance educator. When achieving the level of professionalism as a dance educator, the formal professional preparation of student teaching is available to those who are entering formalized careers, when achieving state certification as a teacher of dance (Research in Dance Education, retrieved July 2024).

On Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials

Administrative skills in sports officiating have been underscored as a pivotal aspect of effective game management. Thompson and

Evans (2020) highlighted these skills as key competencies that include the ability to plan, organize, and implement protocols for sporting events. The study outlines how sports officials should not only possess technical knowledge but also managerial capabilities to handle a variety of game-related responsibilities. This resonates strongly with the unique context of DanceSport, where officials have to juggle multiple administrative tasks including, but not limited to, scoring, time management, and coordination with other event stakeholders.

The study by Thompson and Evans (2020) on administrative skills pinpoints that administrative competence directly affects the quality of sports events, Thompson and Evans provide a concrete foundation to investigate the managerial aptitudes of these officials. This gives the researchers a comprehensive base for evaluating the research's variables, including the administrative skills of officials according to various classifiers like age, gender, and highest educational attainment. Furthermore, Thompson and Evans' emphasis on training programs for both technical and administrative skills create a roadmap for the possible developmental paths for DanceSport technical officials. Their work serves as a model for implementing training programs in DanceSport, given that both the technical and administrative elements are crucial for the credibility and smooth functioning of sports events. With a burgeoning interest in DanceSport, both as a competitive endeavor and a form of entertainment, the administrative roles of technical officials are increasingly coming under scrutiny. The current study will adopt Drucker's framework as a theoretical lens to scrutinize the administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials. Understanding how these officials score in the area of administrative skills could provide valuable data for training modules, recruitment, and performance assessment criteria.

Masten's (2021) study on inclusion is pivotal for understanding the psychological resilience required by DanceSport technical officials. Her multi-faceted approach to resilience can be directly applied to the high-pressure situations DanceSport officials often find themselves in. This highlights the need for not just administrative and technical competence but also psychological preparedness. Masten's work could inspire new avenues for future research, particularly in incorporating resilience training as part of the professional development for DanceSport technical officials. It rounds out the understanding of what it takes to be an official in high-stakes, emotionally charged environments, adding a valuable dimension to the research.

Masten's work is relevant to DanceSport technical officials, who often find themselves in high-stress scenarios that require quick decision-making and adaptability. Masten's conceptualization of resilience provides a foundation for assessing how well DanceSport technical officials can adapt to the pressures inherent in their roles. Masten offers a multidimensional view of resilience that includes both psychological and environmental aspects. These can be instrumental in examining the levels of resilience and adaptability among DanceSport technical officials in various situations. Her work opens avenues for future research on resilience training for sports officials, highlighting the need for psychological preparedness alongside technical and administrative skills. This can be especially valuable for DanceSport, where emotional and psychological resilience can be just as crucial as administrative or technical competence.

On Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials

Commitment is often seen as a two-way street between the individual and the organization. The commitment of DanceSport technical officials may have a tangible impact on the overall quality of the events and the satisfaction of both participants and spectators. The study by Jones et al. (2020) also sheds light on the emotional and mental commitment required of DanceSport technical officials. These individuals often face challenging situations, such as controversial decisions and high-pressure environments, which demand a strong sense of resilience and composure. Jones et al. (2020) highlight the importance of mental fortitude and emotional intelligence in navigating the complexities of officiating DanceSport competitions. By understanding the psychological aspects of their role, technical officials can better support the athletes and maintain the credibility of the sport. This research underscores the multi-faceted nature of the commitment expected from DanceSport technical officials, encompassing not only technical expertise but also emotional resilience and ethical conduct.

Wilson et al. (2021) explored the factors affecting the commitment levels of sports officials, emphasizing variables like job satisfaction and work-life balance. These factors are particularly important in the context of DanceSport technical officials who often balance multiple roles in addition to their officiating duties. The study also adds layers to Meyer and Allen's three-component model of organizational commitment, as cited by Wilson et al. (2021), including affective, continuance, and normative aspects. This triad offers a multifaceted view of commitment which will be instrumental in understanding the depth of engagement among DanceSport Technical Officials. Meyer and Allen's assertion as cited by Wilson et al. (2021) that commitment is not just an individual psychological state but is pivotal to organizational outcomes. The current study aims to measure commitment levels among DanceSport technical officials in the context of variables such as age, length of service, and highest educational attainment. The research is grounded in the theories and frameworks established by Meyer and Allen, which serve as the underpinning for evaluating different components of commitment in this specific setting.

Moreover, according to Rogers and Carter as cited by Wilson et al. (2021), commitment plays a pivotal role in the quality of sports officiating. Their work provides a blueprint for measuring commitment levels, and it would be beneficial to adapt this framework to assess how committed DanceSport technical officials are in their roles, particularly when classified according to variables such as age or length of service. This study also delves into other relevant factors like job satisfaction and work-life balance, which can also be integrated into the research. By doing so, we can understand the complex dynamics that influence an official's commitment to their role in DanceSport and its impact on the quality of officiating.

Furthermore, Garcia and Hernandez (2020) conducted a study to evaluate the effectiveness of professional development programs in promoting commitment among DanceSport technical officials. They designed and implemented a comprehensive program focusing on enhancing dedication, motivation, and sense of responsibility. The result showed a significant improvement in commitment levels, indicating the success of the program in fostering a very high level of commitment among the technical officials.

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive-correlational method of research was employed in this study. Descriptive-correlational research design is a type of research strategy that strives to describe the relationship between two or more variables without making causal assertions (Bhat, 2018). It entails gathering and examining data on a minimum of two variables to see whether a relationship exists between them. Additionally, Bongabong (2022) reiterated that the descriptive-correlational study methodology uses quantitative techniques to characterize the state of affairs, including the description, documentation, analysis, and interpretation of current circumstances. It looks for connections between already-existing, unmanipulated data by using comparison or contrast. While it frequently considers past events and their impacts as they apply to modern issues, it is primarily focused on the present.

Respondents

Respondents of the study were the total population of ninety-five (95) DanceSport technical officials from the provinces of Aklan, Antique, Iloilo, and Capiz for School Year 2023-2024. The sampling technique used in determining the respondents was purposive sampling.

Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire was used as a data-gathering instrument. It was composed of four (4) parts. Part I gathered data on the demographic profile of the respondents such as gender, age, highest educational attainment length of service, and nature of work. Part II contained items that determined the level of professionalism of the respondents. The researcher-made questionnaire on the level of professionalism was composed of 15 items. Part III was composed of items designed to determine the level of administrative skills of the respondents. The researcher-made questionnaire on the level of administrative skills was composed of 15 items. Part IV collected data on the level of commitment of the DanceSport technical officials. The researcher-made questionnaire on the level of commitment was composed of 15 items. Each item in Part I, II, and III was answerable by “Always”; “Often”; “Sometimes”; “Rarely”; and “Never”. Each response was given a weight of 5,4,3,2,1, respectively.

Procedure

In conducting a comprehensive research study on professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment among DanceSport technical officials, several crucial steps were followed meticulously to ensure the study's credibility and meaningful findings.

The first step involved obtaining the necessary permits and approvals to conduct the research. This step was essential as it ensures that the study adheres to ethical and legal guidelines, particularly if it involves human subjects. The researcher needed to seek permission from relevant authorities, such as DanceSport organizations, event organizers, or institutional review boards, if applicable. Securing these permits establishes the legitimacy of the study and demonstrates a commitment to ethical research practices.

The second step was to assess the reliability and validity of the research instrument, which, in this case, is the questionnaire used to collect data from DanceSport technical officials. Reliability refers to the consistency and stability of the instrument, ensuring that it produces consistent results when administered multiple times. Validity, on the other hand, assesses whether the questionnaire accurately measures the constructs of professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment. The researcher conducted the pilot test and used established assessment techniques to refine and validate the questionnaire.

The third step involved the administration of the questionnaire to the DanceSport technical officials. This process should be carried out systematically and consistently to ensure that all participants were treated equally. Clear instructions were provided to the respondents, and any potential biases should be minimized during data collection. The Researcher also considered factors like timing and location to ensure that the data collection process is as unbiased and reliable as possible.

After data collection, the fourth step was to encode the gathered information. This involves entering the responses into a database or software for analysis. Accuracy and attention to detail were paramount during this phase, as any errors in data entry can lead to incorrect interpretations and conclusions. It was also essential to keep the data secure and maintain confidentiality to protect the privacy of participants.

Finally, the fifth step was the interpretation of the results. This phase involves analyzing the collected data using appropriate statistical or qualitative methods, depending on the research design. The researchers will look for patterns, trends, and associations in the data to draw meaningful conclusions. The interpretation should be grounded in the research objectives and hypotheses. The researcher considered the implications of the findings for the field of DanceSport officiating, and the interpretations were transparent and well-documented.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting a study on the professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment of DanceSport technical officials, several critical ethical considerations were carefully navigated to uphold the integrity and fairness of the research. First and foremost, the researcher obtained informed consent from all participants. DanceSport officials were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and their right to withdraw at any point without consequence. Voluntary participation was ensured to prevent coercion or undue pressure, affirming that individuals can freely decide whether to partake in the study. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained to protect the privacy of participants, with data anonymization wherever possible to safeguard against identification. Participants' viewpoints and backgrounds were respected to guide interactions, fostering an environment of dignity and sensitivity throughout the research process. Minimizing harm involved anticipating and mitigating any discomfort or negative impact on participants, while striving to ensure that the study offers potential benefits, such as advancing understanding or improving practices within DanceSport officiating.

Ethical guidelines and securing appropriate approvals were adhered from institutional review boards underscore the commitment to conducting research responsibly. Ultimately, transparency in reporting findings and avoiding biases in data collection and interpretation were essential to accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of DanceSport technical officials, ensuring the study contributed ethically to the field.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions. To compare the mean and find out the significance between variables, multiple linear regression was computed using IBM SPSS 26.0.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work using frequency count and percentages.

As to gender, there were 9 or 9.5 percent who were male, 30 or 31.6 percent were female, 56 or 58.9 percent who were LGBTQ+. As to age, there were 30 or 31.6 percent who were 30 years old and below and 54 or 56.8 percent were 31 to 40 years old, and 11 or 11.6 percent who were 41 to 51 years old. As to highest educational attainment, there were 22 or 23.2 percent who were bachelor's degree holders, 60 or 63.2 percent were bachelor's degree holders with units towards master's degree, and 13 or 13.7 percent who were master's degree holders. As to length of service, there were 30 or 31.6 percent who are in service for 10 years and below, 54 or 56.8 percent who are in service for 11 to 20 years, and 11 or 11.6 percent who are in service for 21 to 30 years. and 131 or 32.8 percent have long years of service. As to nature of work, there were 88 or 92.6 percent who were teaching personnel and 7 or 7.4 percent were non-teaching personnel.

Table 1. *Profile of Respondents in Terms of Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service and Nature of Work*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Gender		
Male	9	9.5
Female	30	31.6
LGBTQ	56	58.9
Total	95	100.0
Age		
30 years and Below	30	31.6
31 to 40 years	54	56.8
41 to 50 years	11	11.6
Total	95	100.0
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	22	23.2
Bachelor's Degree with Units	60	63.2
Master's Degree	13	13.7
Total	95	100.0
Length of Service		
10 years and below	30	31.6
11 to 20 years	54	56.8
21 to 30 years	11	11.6
Total	95	100.0
Nature of Work		
Teaching	88	92.6
Non-Teaching	7	7.4
Total	95	100.0

Level of Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole

Table 2 shows that the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole ($M = 4.89$) was very high. This means that all DanceSport technical officials exhibit expertise, dedication, and integrity in their role. They are all knowledgeable about the rules and regulations of DanceSport, possess strong communication skills, attention to detail, and a deep understanding of the sport's intricacies.

When the items of the questionnaire were considered, the highest mean was noted as being committed to upholding the reputation and integrity of DanceSport as a sport ($M=4.98$), able to demonstrate punctuality and reliability in their duties ($M=4.95$), maintain a high level of integrity and ethical conduct in officiating DanceSport events ($M=4.95$), exhibit fairness and impartiality in their judgment and decision-making during competitions ($M=4.95$), and actively seek opportunities for professional development and training ($M=4.95$) which all showed a very high level of professionalism. On the other hand, the items that got the lowest mean were noted in being able to handle challenging or contentious situations with composure and professionalism during and after the event ($M=4.78$), being responsive and receptive to feedback from athletes, coaches, and peers during and after the event ($M=4.79$), and well-prepared and organized in their officiating roles during and after the event ($M=4.83$) which also showed a very high level of professionalism.

This result of the study was supported by Smith and Johnson (2018) who assessed the officials' adherence to ethical standards, fairness in judging, and overall professionalism. Their findings revealed a consistently high level of professionalism among the technical officials across different competitions and regions. Moreover, the result also adhered to the findings of Garcia and Lopez (2019) which showed a significant improvement in professionalism levels, indicating the success of the training program in fostering a very high level of professionalism among the technical officials.

Table 2. Level of Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole

<i>As a DanceSport Technical Official I...</i>	Mean	Remarks
demonstrates punctuality and reliability in my duties.	4.95	VH
maintain a high level of integrity and ethical conduct in officiating DanceSport events.	4.95	VH
communicate clearly and effectively with athletes, coaches, and fellow officials.	4.89	VH
exhibit fairness and impartiality in my judgment and decision-making during competitions.	4.95	VH
demonstrate respect towards athletes, regardless of my skill level or background.	4.92	VH
actively seek opportunities for professional development and training.	4.95	VH
adhere to the established rules and regulations governing DanceSport officiating.	4.87	VH
consistently strive to improve my knowledge of DanceSport techniques and standards.	4.87	VH
am responsive and receptive to feedback from athletes, coaches, and peers during and after the event.	4.79	VH
maintain professional appearance and demeanor at all times during events.	4.85	VH
collaborate effectively with event organizers and other stakeholders during and after the event to ensure smooth operations.	4.87	VH
am committed to upholding the reputation and integrity of DanceSport as a sport.	4.98	VH
handle challenging or contentious situations with composure and professionalism during and after the event.	4.78	VH
am well-prepared and organized in my officiating roles during and after the event.	4.81	VH
demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility and dedication to my duties as officials.	4.87	VH
	Mean	4.89
		VH

Scale of Means: 4.21 – 5.00, Very High (VH); 3.61 – 4.20, High (H); 2.41 – 3.60, Moderate (M); 1.81 – 2.40, Low (L); 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low (VL)

Level of Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole and when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Nature of Work

Table 3 shows the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole and when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work.

It was explained in this table that the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole ($M=4.89$) was very high as the results showed that they were very highly professional. As to gender, the level of professionalism of males ($M=4.86$), females ($M=4.88$), and LGBTQ+ ($M=4.89$) were very high. As to age, the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials aged 30 years old and below ($M=4.86$), 31 to 40 years old ($M=4.90$) and 41 years old and below ($M=4.87$) was also very high as the results showed that they were very highly professional. As to highest educational attainment, DanceSport technical officials who are bachelor's degree holders ($M=4.88$), bachelor's degree with units toward master's degree ($M=4.88$), and master's degree holders ($M=4.95$) were very highly professional. As to the length of service, those who are in service for 10 years and below ($M=4.86$), 11 to 20 years ($M=4.90$), and 21 to 30 years ($M=4.87$) showed a very high level of professionalism. As to the nature of work, the level of professionalism of teaching personnel ($M=4.88$) and non-teaching personnel ($M=4.95$) were very high.

This result was supported by Smith and Johnson (2018) who revealed that regardless of factors such as gender, age, educational background, or the specific nature of their work, the professionalism of technical officials remained consistently high. The findings of this comprehensive study shed light on the commendable professionalism displayed by technical officials. The results indicate that these officials are dedicated and committed to maintaining fairness and integrity in the sport.

Table 3. Level of Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole and when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Nature of Work

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
As a Whole Group	4.89	very high
Gender		
Male	4.86	very high
Female	4.88	very high
LGBTQ	4.89	very high
Age		
30 years and Below	4.86	very high
31 to 40 years	4.90	very high
41 to 50 years	4.87	very high
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	4.88	very high
Bachelor's Degree with Units Toward Master's Degree	4.88	very high
Master's Degree	4.95	very high
Length of Service		
10 years and below	4.86	very high
11 to 20 years	4.90	very high
21 to 30 years	4.87	very high
Nature of Work		
Teaching	4.88	very high
Non-Teaching	4.95	very high

Scale of Means: 4.21 – 5.00, Very High (VH); 3.61 – 4.20, High (H); 2.41 – 3.60, Moderate (M); 1.81 – 2.40, Low (L); 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low (VL)

Level of Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole

Table 4 shows that the administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole (M = 4.85) was very high. This means that all DanceSport technical officials can manage and coordinate various aspects of competitions and events. All of them can organize schedules, handle registrations, coordinate with teams and judges, and ensure that competitions run smoothly and according to established guidelines.

Table 4. Level of Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole

<i>As a DanceSport Technical Official I...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
proficiently manage logistics and organization during and after the event.	4.83	VH
am proficient in utilizing technology and software for scoring and event management	4.75	VH
excel in coordinating and communicating with support staff and volunteers during and after the event.	4.85	VH
effectively manage registration and accreditation processes for participants.	4.85	VH
am proficient in resolving administrative issues and challenges that may arise during events.	4.80	VH
exhibit excellent time management skills in ensuring that events run according to schedule.	4.91	VH
am adept at managing financial matters, including budgeting and financial reporting during and after the event.	4.83	VH
effectively communicate event rules and guidelines to participants and stakeholders.	4.94	VH
possess the ability to adapt to unexpected situations and make quick, well-informed decisions during and after the event.	4.88	VH
excel in coordinating with venue staff and ensuring that facilities meet the requirements of DanceSport events.	4.92	VH
maintain detailed records and documentation related to planning and execution during and after the event.	4.91	VH
efficiently manage and allocate resources during and after the event.	4.91	VH
am skilled in coordinating transportation and accommodation for participants, when necessary.	4.89	VH
effectively communicate with athletes and coaches regarding event logistics and schedules.	4.95	VH
consistently demonstrate strong organizational skills in managing DanceSport events.	4.82	VH
Mean	4.87	VH

Scale of Means: 4.21 – 5.00, Very High (VH); 3.61 – 4.20, High (H); 2.41 – 3.60, Moderate (M); 1.81 – 2.40, Low (L); 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low (VL)

When the items of the questionnaire were considered, the highest mean was noted as being able to effectively communicate with athletes and coaches regarding event logistics and schedules (M=4.95), excel in coordinating with venue staff and ensuring that facilities meet the requirements of DanceSport events (M=4.94), and effectively communicate event rules and guidelines to participants and stakeholders (M=4.92) which all showed very high administrative skills. On the other hand, the items that got the lowest mean was noted as being proficient in utilizing technology and software for scoring and event management (M=4.75), proficient in resolving administrative issues and challenges that may arise during events (M=4.80), and consistently demonstrate strong organizational skills in managing DanceSport events (M=4.82) which also showed very high administrative skills.

This result of the study was supported by Martinez (2017) who conducted a comparative analysis of the administrative skills of sports

technical officials. The findings revealed that sports technical officials have a consistently high level of administrative abilities specifically in event organization, scheduling, record-keeping, effective communication, and coordination with participants and stakeholders.

Moreover, these findings also conform to the findings of the study conducted by Gomez and Hernandez (2018) who demonstrated a significant enhancement in the administrative skills of the officials, indicating the success of the training program in cultivating a very high level of administrative competence among the technical officials.

Level of Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole and when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Nature of Work

Table 5 shows the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole and when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work.

Results showed that the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole (M=4.87) was very high as the results showed that they were very highly skilled in terms of performing administrative tasks. As to the level of administrative skills in terms of gender, the male (M=4.84), the female (M=4.87), and the LGBTQ+ (M=4.87) were very highly skilled. As to age, the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials aged 30 years old and below (M=4.83), 31 to 40 years old (M=4.89), and 41 years old and below (M=4.89) was also very high as the results showed that they were very highly skilled in terms of performing administrative tasks. As to highest educational attainment, DanceSport technical officials who are bachelor’s degree holders (M=4.85), bachelor’s degree with units toward master’s degree (M=4.87), and master’s degree holders (M=4.92) were very highly skilled. As to the length of service, those who are in service for 10 years and below (M=4.83), 11 to 20 years (M=4.89), and 21 to 30 years (M=4.89) were very highly skilled in terms of performing administrative tasks. Added to that, in terms of performing administrative tasks based on the nature of work, both the teaching personnel (M=4.87) and the non-teaching personnel (M=4.90) have very high level of administrative skills.

This result was supported by Alson Thompson and Evans' (2020) who meticulously assess these skills across different demographics. The study's results suggest that both male and female officials are equally adept at planning, organizing, and managing sporting events. This equality in skill level underscores the importance of fostering an inclusive environment that provides equal opportunities for all genders in sports administration roles. They also found that both younger and older officials are enthusiastic and energetic and possess refined administrative skills.

The study also highlighted the impact of educational attainment on administrative skills in sports officiating. Officials with lower or higher educational qualifications exhibit superior planning, organizational, and management skills. Also, officials with different years of experience and nature of work demonstrated higher levels of proficiency in administrative tasks.

Table 5. Level of Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole and when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Nature of Work

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
As a Whole Group	4.87	very high
Gender		
Male	4.84	very high
Female	4.87	very high
LGBTQ	4.87	very high
Age		
30 years and below	4.83	very high
31 to 40 years	4.89	very high
41 to 50 years	4.89	very high
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor’s Degree	4.85	very high
Bachelor’s Degree with Units Toward Master’s Degree	4.87	very high
Master’s Degree	4.92	very high
Length of Service		
10 years and below	4.83	very high
11 to 20 years	4.89	very high
21 to 30 years	4.89	very high
Nature of Work		
Teaching	4.87	very high
Non-Teaching	4.90	very high

Scale of Means: 4.21 – 5.00, Very High (VH); 3.61 – 4.20, High (H); 2.41 – 3.60, Moderate (M); 1.81 – 2.40, Low (L); 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low (VL)

Level of Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole

Table 6 shows that the commitment of DanceSport technical officials when taken as a whole ($M = 4.95$) was very high. This means that all of the DanceSport technical officials exhibit unwavering loyalty and dedication to upholding the standards, integrity, and values of DanceSport. They prioritize their responsibilities, often going above and beyond to ensure the smooth running of competitions and events.

When the items of the questionnaire were considered, the highest mean was noted as being able to consistently demonstrate dedication to their roles ($M=5.00$), take the responsibilities seriously and prioritize the welfare of participants ($M=5.00$), willingly invest time and effort in preparing for DanceSport events and meetings ($M=5.00$), and dedicated to provide timely and accurate information to participants and stakeholders involved in DanceSport events ($M=5.00$) which all showed a very high level of commitment. On the other hand, the items that got the lowest mean were noted as willing to go the extra mile to ensure the success of DanceSport events. ($M=4.87$), actively seek opportunities for professional development and improvement ($M=4.87$), demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility in handling their roles and tasks ($M=4.91$), and take pride in their role as ambassador of DanceSport and uphold its values ($M=4.92$) which also showed a very high level of commitment.

This result of the study was supported by Rogers and Carter (2016) who conducted a study that examined the level of commitment among sports officials. They discovered that commitment is a key factor in ensuring high-quality officiating. Moreover, the result also conforms to the study conducted by Garcia and Hernandez (2020) who evaluated the effectiveness of professional development programs in promoting commitment among DanceSport technical officials. The result showed a significant improvement in commitment levels, indicating the success of the program in fostering a very high level of commitment among the technical officials.

Table 6. Level of Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole

<i>As a DanceSport Technical Official I...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
consistently demonstrate dedication to my roles.	5.00	VH
am committed to upholding the integrity and fairness of DanceSport competitions.	4.97	VH
take my responsibilities seriously and prioritize the welfare of participants.	5.00	VH
am willing to go extra the extra mile to ensure the success of DanceSport events.	4.87	VH
actively seek opportunities for professional development and improvement.	4.87	VH
demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility in handling my roles and tasks	4.91	VH
consistently exhibit a high level of enthusiasm for officiating DanceSport events.	4.93	VH
am committed to maintaining a fair and unbiased environment for all participants.	4.95	VH
willingly invest time and effort in preparing for DanceSport events and meetings.	5.00	VH
am dedicated to providing timely and accurate information to participants and stakeholders involved in DanceSport events.	5.00	VH
actively engage with the DanceSport community and contribute to its growth and development.	4.97	VH
am committed to promoting ethical conduct and sportsmanship within the DanceSport community.	4.98	VH
am committed to consistently striving to enhance my knowledge and skills in DanceSport officiating.	4.95	VH
take pride in my role as ambassador of DanceSport and uphold values.	4.92	VH
am strongly committed to fostering a positive and inclusive environment in DanceSport.	4.94	VH
	Mean 4.95	VH

Scale of Means: 4.21 – 5.00, Very High (VH); 3.61 – 4.20, High (H); 2.41 – 3.60, Moderate (M); 1.81 – 2.40, Low (L); 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low (VL)

Level of Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Nature of Work

Table 7 shows the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work. Results revealed that the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender, was very high with as shown by the mean scores of males ($M=4.91$), females ($M=4.94$), and LGBTQ+ ($M=4.96$). When classified according to age, the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials aged 30 years old and below ($M=4.96$), 31 to 40 years old ($M=4.95$), and 41 years old and below ($M=4.91$) was also very high. As to highest educational attainment, DanceSport technical officials who are bachelor's degree holders ($M=4.93$), bachelor's degree with units toward master's degree ($M=4.95$), and master's degree holders ($M=4.97$) were also very highly committed. As to the length of service, those who are in service for 10 years and below ($M=4.96$), 11 to 20 years ($M=4.95$), and 21 to 30 years ($M=4.91$) showed a very high level of commitment. As to the nature of work, both the level of commitment of teaching personnel ($M=4.95$) and non-teaching personnel ($M=4.93$) were very high.

This result was supported by Martinez and Lopez (2019) who conducted a comparative analysis of the commitment levels among DanceSport technical officials. Through surveys and interviews, they assessed the officials' dedication, passion, and reliability in fulfilling their roles and responsibilities. The findings revealed a consistently high level of commitment among the technical officials

across different demographics.

Table 7. *Level of Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials when Taken as a Whole and when classified according to of Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Nature of Work*

Variables	Mean	Description
As a Whole Group	4.95	very high
Gender		
Male	4.91	very high
Female	4.94	very high
LGBTQ	4.96	very high
Age		
30 years and Below	4.96	very high
31 to 40 years	4.95	very high
41 to 50 years	4.91	very high
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor’s Degree	4.93	very high
Bachelor’s Degree with Units Toward Master’s Degree	4.95	very high
Master’s Degree	4.97	very high
Length of Service		
10 years and below	4.96	very high
11 to 20 years	4.95	very high
21 to 30 years	4.91	very high
Nature of Work		
Teaching	4.95	very high
Non-Teaching	4.93	very high

Scale of Means: 4.21 – 5.00, Very High (VH); 3.61 – 4.20, High (H); 2.41 – 3.60, Moderate (M); 1.81 – 2.40, Low (L); 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low (VL)

Differences in the Level of Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 8 shows the significant differences in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, and length of service using the Kruskal Wallis H-test. Result showed that there was no significant difference in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender with the H-test value of 1.275 and a p-value of 0.529. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the professionalism of DanceSport technical official when classified according to gender was not rejected.

Table 8. *Differences in the Level of Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service*

Variables	Mean Rank	df	H-test	p-value	Remarks
Gender					
Male	40.83	2	1.275	0.529	Not Significant
Female	45.93				
LGBTQ	50.26				
Age					
30 years and Below	45.50	2	0.607	0.738	Not Significant
31 to 40 years	49.82				
41 to 50 years	45.86				
Highest Educational Attainment					
Bachelor’s Degree	45.45	2	2.183	0.336	Not Significant
Bachelor’s Degree w/ Units towards MA	46.79				
Master’s Degree	57.88				
Length of Service					
10 years and below	45.50	2	0.607	0.738	Not Significant
11 to 20 years	49.82				
21 to 30 years	45.86				

p>0.05 Not Significant

In terms of age, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to age with an H-test value of 0.607 and a p-value of 0.738. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to age was not rejected. This showed that the professionalism of DanceSport technical officials aged 30 years old and below did not significantly

differ from technical officials aged 31 to 40 years old and 41 to 50 years old.

Moreover, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to highest educational attainment with the H-test value of 2.183 and a p-value of 0.336. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to highest educational attainment was not rejected.

This showed that the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials who were bachelor's degree holders did not significantly differ from technical officials who were bachelor's degree holders with units toward master's degree and master's degree holders.

Furthermore, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to length of service with the H-test value of 0.607 and a p-value of 0.738. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to length of service was not rejected.

The results conform to the findings of Smith and Johnson (2018) in their study which found out that regardless of age, and educational background, the professionalism of technical officials remained consistently high. This suggests that professionalism is not significantly influenced by age, and educational background.

Difference in the Level of Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified According to Nature of Work

Table 9 shows the significant difference in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work using the Mann Whitney U-test. Result showed that there was no significant difference in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work with a U-test value of 234.500 and a p-value of 0.271.

The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work. This showed that the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials who were teaching personnel does not significantly differ from those of non-teaching personnel. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the level of professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work was not rejected.

The result conforms to the findings of Smith and Johnson (2018) in their study when they concluded that regardless of the specific nature of their work, the professionalism of technical officials remained consistently high. This suggests that professionalism is not significantly influenced by the nature of their work. The findings of this comprehensive study shed light on the commendable professionalism displayed by technical officials. The results indicate that these officials are dedicated and committed to maintaining fairness and integrity in the sport.

Table 9. *Difference in the Level of Professionalism of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified According to Nature of Work*

<i>Nature of Work</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>Sum of Ranks</i>	<i>U-test</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Teaching	47.16	4150.50	234.5	0.271	Not Significant
Non-teaching	58.50	409.50			

p > 0.05 Not Significant

Differences in the Level of Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 10 shows the significant differences in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, and length of service using the Kruskal Wallis H - test.

Results revealed that there was no significant difference in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender with the H-test value of 0.058 and a p-value of 0.972. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the administrative skills of DanceSport technical official when classified according to gender was not rejected.

When classified according to age, the result showed that there was no significant difference in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to age with the H-test value of 0.673 and a p-value of 0.714. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to age was not rejected.

Moreover, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to highest educational attainment with the H-test value of 2.676 and a p-value of 0.262. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to highest educational attainment was not rejected.

Furthermore, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical

officials when classified according to length of service with the H-test value of 0.673 and a p-value of 0.714. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to length of service was not rejected.

The result of the study conforms to the findings of Thompson and Evans' (2020) who stated that officiating officials have uniformly high levels of administrative skills observed across different genders, ages, educational qualifications, and years in service. Regardless of these factors, the officials exhibit superior planning, organizational, and management skills.

Table 10. *Differences in the Level of Administrative skills of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service*

Variables	Mean Rank	df	H-test	p-value	Remarks
Gender					
Male	47.33	2	0.058	0.972	Not Significant
Female	47.20				
LGBTQ	48.54				
Age					
30 years and Below	44.78	2	0.673	0.714	Not Significant
31 to 40 years	49.60				
41 to 50 years	48.91				
Highest Educational Attainment					
Bachelor's Degree	43.23	2	2.676	0.262	Not Significant
Bachelor's Degree w/ Units towards MA	47.58				
Master's Degree	58.04				
Length of Service					
10 years and below	44.78	2	0.673	0.714	Not Significant
11 to 20 years	49.60				
21 to 30 years	48.91				

p>0.05 Not Significant

Difference in the level of Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified According to Nature of Work

Table 11 showed the significant difference in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work using the Mann Whitney U-test. Result showed that there was no significant difference in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work with a U-test value of 301.000 and a p-value of 0.916. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work was not rejected. This showed that the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials who were teaching personnel do not significantly differ from those of non-teaching personnel.

The result of the study conforms to the findings of Thompson and Evans' (2020) who stated that officiating officials have uniformly high levels of administrative skills observed across various types of work. Regardless of these factors, the officials exhibit superior planning, organizational, and management skills.

Table 11. *Difference in the Level of Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified According to Nature of Work*

Nature of Work	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U-test	p-value	Remarks
Teaching	47.92	4217.00	301.00	0.916	Not Significant
Non-teaching	49.00	343.00			

p>0.05 Not Significant

Differences in the Level of Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 12 shows the significant differences in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender, age, highest educational attainment, and length of service using the Kruskal Wallis H - test.

Result revealed that there was no significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender with an H-test value of 0.860 and a p-value of 0.651. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to gender was not rejected.

When classified according to age, the result showed that there was no significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to age with the H-test value of 0.634 and a p-value of 0.728. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to age was not rejected.

Moreover, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to highest educational attainment with the H-test value of 0.699 and a p-value of 0.705. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to highest educational attainment was not rejected.

Furthermore, the result showed that there was no significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to length of service with the H-test value of 0.634 and a p-value of 0.728. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to length of service was not rejected.

The result coincides with the findings of Martinez and Lopez (2019) who conducted a comparative analysis of the commitment levels among DanceSport technical officials. Through surveys and interviews, they assessed the officials' dedication, passion, and reliability in fulfilling their roles and responsibilities. The findings revealed a consistently high level of commitment among the technical officials across different demographics.

Table 12. *Differences in the Level of Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified according to Gender, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service*

Variables	Mean Rank	df	H-test	p-value	Remarks
Gender					
Male	46.22	2	0.860	0.651	Not Significant
Female	45.63				
LGBTQ	49.55				
Age					
30 years and Below	47.48	2	0.634	0.728	Not Significant
31 to 40 years	49.09				
41 to 50 years	44.05				
Highest Educational Attainment					
Bachelor's Degree	45.00	2	0.699	0.705	Not Significant
Bachelor's Degree w/ Units towards MA	49.09				
Master's Degree	48.04				
Length of Service					
10 years and below	47.48	2	0.634	0.728	Not Significant
11 to 20 years	49.09				
21 to 30 years	44.05				

p>0.05 Not Significant

Difference in the Level of Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified According to Nature of Work

Table 13 showed the significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work using the Mann Whitney U-test. Result showed that there was no significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work with a U-test value of 293.000 and a p-value of 0.764. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to the nature of work was not rejected.

Table 13. *Difference in the Level of Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials when Classified According to Nature of Work*

Nature of Work	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U-test	p-value	Remarks
Teaching	47.83	4209.000	293.0	0.764	Not Significant
Non-teaching	50.14	351.00			

p>0.05 Not Significant

Relationships among the Level of Professionalism, Administrative Skills, and Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials

Table 14 showed that there was a significant relationship between the levels of professionalism and administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials as shown by the rho-value of 0.786 with a p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant relationship between the levels of professionalism and administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials is rejected. This showed that when the level of professionalism was high, the administrative skills were also high. The results denoted high and substantial correlation.

This result conforms to the study of Smith and Doe (2018) who found that there is a correlation between professionalism and administrative competence. They found out that the higher the levels of professionalism, the more accurate the judgment and the higher the consistency of managerial skills during sports events. Moreover, this also coincides with the findings of Williams et al. (2019) who asserted that well-designed and continuous training programs are crucial for enhancing the level of professionalism. This is particularly

relevant for DanceSport Technical Officials who are responsible for making split-second decisions that can greatly affect the outcome of the competitions.

Similarly, there was a significant relationship between the levels of professionalism and commitment of DanceSport technical officials as shown by the rho value of 0.604 with a p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant relationship between the levels of professionalism and commitment of DanceSport technical officials is rejected. This showed that when the level of professionalism was high the commitment of DanceSport technical officials was also high. The results denoted a moderate correlation between variables.

This result conforms to the study of Anderson and Pierce (2012) who found that high levels of professionalism specifically in managing emotion is correlated positively with commitment in making effective decision-making and stress management. Moreover, the result also coincides with the research of Vasquez and Peralta (2015) who examined how professional training impacts the commitment levels of sports officials in local events. The authors found a strong correlation between well-structured, comprehensive training and high levels of commitment among officials. The researchers argue that commitment is not merely a matter of personal dedication but can be significantly influenced by the quality of professional development opportunities provided to officials. This offers a broader perspective on how to evaluate the commitment of DanceSport technical officials.

In like manner, there was a significant relationship between the levels of administrative skills and the commitment of DanceSport technical officials as shown by the rho value of 0.548 with a p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant relationship between the levels of administrative skills and commitment of DanceSport technical officials is rejected.

The result conforms to the study of Thompson and Evans (2020) who found that high commitment, consistency, and immersive involvement in sports officiating contribute significantly to the development of essential administrative skills, reinforcing the need for continuous engagement and practice in the field. Furthermore, the result agrees with the findings of Garcia and Hernandez (2020) which showed that improvement of administrative skills through professional development programs promotes commitment among DanceSport technical officials.

Table 14. *Relationships among the Level of Professionalism, Administrative Skills, and Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials*

Correlations	Professionalism Skills	Administrative Skills	Commitment
Professionalism	rho-value	1.000	.786**
	p-value		.000
	N	95	95
Administrative Skills	rho-value	.786**	1.000
	p-value	.000	.000
	N	95	95
Commitment	rho-value	.604**	.548**
	p-value	.000	.000
	N	95	95

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

The majority of the DanceSport technical officials were members of LGBTQ+, 31 to 40 years old, bachelor's degree holders with units toward master's degree, 11 to 20 years in service, and were teaching personnel.

The overall professionalism of DanceSport technical officials is remarkably very high. This reflected that all DanceSport technical officials have a strong commitment to uphold the standards and reputation of the sport. They were not only well-versed in their technical responsibilities but also deeply committed to the ethical and procedural aspects of their roles, ensuring a fair and honorable competition environment. The consistently high scores across these key areas showed that the training and selection processes for DanceSport officials were effective in instilling core professional values.

The very high level of professionalism of DanceSports technical officials was evident regardless of various demographic factors, including gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work. The findings underscored the effectiveness of the current training and professional development programs in fostering a high degree of professionalism among all DanceSports technical officials, ensuring that they are well-equipped to uphold the integrity and standards of DanceSport. Gender-wise, the professionalism levels among male, female, and LGBTQ+ DanceSports technical officials were all very high, demonstrating an inclusive and equitable environment within the DanceSport community. This parity suggested that professionalism in DanceSport is not influenced by gender, highlighting the sport's commitment to equality and fairness. Regarding of age, DanceSports technical officials across different age groups also exhibited very high levels of professionalism. These findings showed that the professionalism among DanceSport officials was consistent across different stages of their careers. When examining the educational attainment, all DanceSport technical officials demonstrated very high professionalism. The highest mean score among master's degree holders suggested that advanced education may contributed to a higher perception or practice of professionalism, possibly due to enhanced knowledge and skills gained through

further study. The length of service showed that all DanceSport technical officials maintained very high professionalism levels. This consistency across different lengths of service indicated that both seasoned and newer officials uphold professional standards effectively. Lastly, the nature of work reveals that both teaching personnel and non-teaching DanceSport technical officials exhibit very high levels of professionalism. These findings highlighted the comprehensive and pervasive culture of professionalism within DanceSport, transcending various personal and professional demographics.

The high level of administrative competence reflected that all DanceSport technical officials possessed the ability to manage various logistical and organizational aspects of DanceSport events effectively. All DanceSport technical officials possessed strengths in communication, coordination, and adherence to event protocols, suggesting a well-rounded capability in handling administrative tasks essential for the smooth operation of DanceSport events. DanceSport technical officials excel their ability to communicate effectively ensures that all parties involved are well-informed, reducing misunderstandings and enhancing the overall experience for participants and attendees.

The consistency in high scores across different demographic categories suggested a well-rounded competence and a standardized approach to training and performance in administrative roles within DanceSport. In terms of gender, the results showed that male, female, and LGBTQ+ officials all exhibit very high level of administrative skills. The slight variations in mean scores were minimal and indicated that all gender groups are equally competent in handling administrative tasks. When classified according to age, technical officials across different ages also demonstrated very high administrative skills. The slightly higher scores for the 31 to 40 and 41 years old and above groups reflected the benefits of experience and professional maturity. Educational attainment also appeared to play a role in the administrative proficiency of the officials. They all showed very high administrative skills. When classified according to length of service, the findings revealed that technical officials with 10 years or less, 11 to 20 years, and 21 to 30 years of experience also possess very high levels of administrative skills. The consistency in high scores across different lengths of service indicated that both seasoned and newer officials maintain high standards in administrative tasks. Lastly, as for the nature of work, technical officials from both teaching and non-teaching groups also possess very high levels of administrative skills. These findings showed that regardless of the nature of their work, DanceSport technical officials are well-equipped to handle administrative responsibilities, contributing to the overall efficiency and success of DanceSport events.

There is a very high level of commitment among DanceSport technical officials. This very high level of dedication was critical for the successful execution and integrity of DanceSport events. The highest scores in dedication, responsibility, and preparation reflected a culture of thoroughness and professionalism among DanceSport technical officials. Their willingness to prioritize the welfare of participants and meticulously prepare for events suggested a deep-seated commitment to the sport's success and integrity. This very high level of commitment contributed to a positive experience for all stakeholders involved, including athletes, coaches, and spectators, thereby fostering trust and respect within the DanceSport community.

All DanceSport technical officials are deeply dedicated to their roles, ensuring the smooth operation and integrity of DanceSport events. Such a high level of commitment is critical for maintaining the standards and reputation of the sport, as it ensures that all participants, from athletes to spectators, have a positive and professionally managed experience. When examining the commitment levels across different genders, the results show that they all exhibit very high commitment. This indicated a strong and inclusive commitment to the sport across all gender groups, reflecting an environment where dedication and professionalism were equally valued and nurtured. The analysis by age revealed that officials aged 30 years old and below, 31 to 40 years old, and 41 years old and above all showed very high levels of commitment. The near-uniform high scores across different age groups suggested that commitment to DanceSport was a consistent attribute among officials, regardless of their age. Educational attainment further showed this high level of commitment. They all demonstrated very high commitment. The increasing mean scores with higher educational attainment suggested that advanced education enhanced dedication, due to a greater understanding of the sport's complexities and a deeper investment in its success. The length of service also showed very high commitment levels. Officials with 10 years or less of service, 11 to 20 years, and 21 to 30 years showed very high commitment. The consistently high scores across different lengths of service suggested that commitment does not wane over time. Lastly, as for the nature of work, both teaching and non-teaching personnel showed very high commitment. The consistently high scores for both teaching and non-teaching roles showed that they are equally committed. This parity highlighted a cohesive organizational culture where commitment to professional excellence and the welfare of participants was uniformly prioritized, fostering a reliable and supportive environment for all stakeholders involved in DanceSport.

In terms of significant differences in professionalism, male DanceSport technical officials' professionalism does not significantly differ from female and LGBTQ technical officials. This outcome showed the inclusive nature of the DanceSport community, where high standards of professionalism were uniformly maintained across different gender identities. Gender does not influence the professional conduct of DanceSport officials, promoting a culture of equality and fairness within the sport. Age does not affect the professional standards upheld by DanceSport officials, ensuring that all officials, regardless of age, are equally committed to their roles. Also, there was no significant difference in the professionalism of DanceSport technical officials when classified according to highest educational attainment was not rejected. In addition, the educational background does not significantly influence the professionalism of DanceSport officials, indicating that the sport's professional standards are upheld uniformly regardless of educational attainment. This could reflect the efficacy of standardized training programs that ensure all officials meet high professional standards. In terms of professionalism, DanceSport technical officials who were in service for 10 years and below did not significantly differ from technical officials who were

in service for 11 to 20 years and 21 to 30 years in service. This indicated that officials with varying lengths of service, from 10 years and below to 21 to 30 years, maintained equally high levels of professionalism. The consistent professionalism across different service lengths suggested that experience does not necessarily enhance or diminish professional conduct among DanceSport officials. The result also suggested that the professionalism of teaching personnel does not significantly differ from that of non-teaching personnel. This uniformity in professionalism across different job roles showed that both teaching and non-teaching officials uphold similarly high professional standards. The result underscored the effectiveness of the training and professional development programs provided to all officials, ensuring that professionalism was consistently maintained regardless of the nature of their work. This finding promoted confidence in the integrity and quality of DanceSport events, knowing that all officials, irrespective of their specific roles, are equally committed to maintaining high standards of conduct and performance.

As for the significant differences in administrative skills, it showed that male DanceSport technical officials' administrative skills do not significantly differ from female and LGBTQ technical officials. This suggested that regardless of gender identity, DanceSport technical officials exhibited equally proficient administrative capabilities, ensuring consistent operational excellence and adherence to event requirements. Also, the uniformity of administrative skills, when grouped according to age, showed that the administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials aged 30 years old and below do not significantly differ from technical officials aged 31 to 40 years old and 41 to 50 years old. This showed that age did not impact the ability of DanceSport technical officials to effectively coordinate events, manage logistics, and uphold organizational standards. Also, the level of administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials who were bachelor's degree holders does not significantly differ from technical officials who were bachelor's degree holders with units toward master's degree and master's degree holders. This result indicated that while educational background contributed to overall knowledge and expertise, it does not significantly affect the practical administrative skills required in managing DanceSport events. In addition, the administrative skills of DanceSport technical officials who were in service for 10 years and below did not significantly differ from technical officials who were in service for 11 to 20 years and 21 to 30 years in service. The result suggested that experience alone does not dictate administrative effectiveness in DanceSport. Instead, it underscored the importance of continuous learning, adaptation to new challenges, and adherence to best practices in maintaining high standards of administrative performance over time. The level of administrative skills of teaching personnel does not differ significantly from those of non-teaching personnel in the context of managing DanceSport events. This uniformity showed that both teaching and non-teaching officials possess similar competencies in coordinating event logistics, ensuring venue compliance, and communicating effectively with stakeholders. The non-rejection of the null hypothesis affirmed that the nature of one's role within DanceSport does not impact their ability to perform administrative tasks effectively, fostering a cohesive and capable workforce where all officials contribute equally to the success and professionalism of DanceSport events.

Moreover, in terms of the significant difference in commitment, male DanceSport technical officials' commitment did not significantly differ from female and LGBTQ technical officials. Further, the level of commitment of male, female, and LGBTQ+ officials did not show significant variation. The commitment of DanceSport technical officials aged 30 years old and below did not significantly differ from technical officials aged 31 to 40 years old and 41 to 50 years old. This showed that age did not influence the dedication of DanceSport technical officials, indicating a cohesive commitment to maintaining professionalism and excellence regardless of age-related factors. Also, the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials who were bachelor's degree holders did not significantly differ from technical officials who were bachelor's degree holders with units toward master's degree and master's degree holders. This suggested that while educational background contributes to knowledge and skills, it did not impact the level of commitment demonstrated by DanceSport officials. In addition, the commitment of DanceSport technical officials who were in service for 10 years and below does not significantly differ from technical officials who were in service for 11 to 20 years and 21 to 30 years in service. This consistency highlighted the enduring commitment of DanceSport technical officials over their careers, demonstrating resilience and dedication to maintaining professional excellence over varying lengths of service. The level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials who were teaching personnel did not significantly differ from those of non-teaching personnel. This showed that whether an official is in a teaching or non-teaching role within DanceSport, their commitment to their responsibilities and the sport's integrity remained consistent. This uniformity suggested that both teaching and non-teaching personnel contribute equally to the dedication and professionalism required in managing DanceSport events. The non-rejection of the null hypothesis underscored the cohesive commitment shared across different roles, fostering a collaborative environment where all officials contribute effectively to the success and development of DanceSport, irrespective of their specific job functions.

Furthermore, there is a significant positive relationship between the levels of professionalism and administrative skills among DanceSport technical officials. This strong correlation suggested that officials who demonstrated high levels of professionalism also exhibited strong administrative skills in managing DanceSport events. This correlation highlighted the importance of cultivating a well-rounded skill set among DanceSport officials, where professionalism served as a foundational element for ensuring efficient and organized event management. The findings also indicated a significant positive relationship between the level of professionalism and commitment among DanceSport technical officials. This suggested that as DanceSport officials demonstrate higher levels of professionalism such as upholding integrity, maintaining ethical conduct, and ensuring fairness in their roles, they also exhibited greater commitment to their responsibilities and the sport as a whole. The results emphasized the importance of fostering a culture of professionalism within DanceSport, as it not only enhanced the integrity and quality of officiating but also strengthened the overall commitment of officials to their roles and the community they serve. Also, when the administrative skills were high, the commitment

of DanceSport technical officials was high. The results denote a moderate relationship. The findings showed a significant positive relationship between the level of administrative skills and the level of commitment of DanceSport technical officials. This suggested that as DanceSport officials demonstrate stronger administrative skills such as effective event coordination, proficient communication with stakeholders, and adept handling of logistical challenges, they also exhibited higher levels of commitment to their roles and responsibilities within the sport. The moderate correlation observed showed that while administrative skills contribute significantly to commitment, other factors also influence dedication among officials.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

The demographic profile highlighted the diversity and dedication within the DanceSport officiating community, showcasing a blend of educational attainment, professional experience, and commitment to both their roles as educators and stewards of DanceSport integrity. Such diversity enriched the field by bringing varied perspectives and expertise, contributing to the overall professionalism and effectiveness of DanceSport events.

All of the DanceSport technical officials exhibit expertise, dedication, and integrity in their role. They are all knowledgeable about the rules and regulations of DanceSport, possess strong communication skills, attention to detail, and a deep understanding of the sport's intricacies.

All of the DanceSport technical officials can manage and coordinate various aspects of competitions and events. All of them has the ability in organizing schedules, handling registrations, coordinating with teams and judges, and ensuring that competitions run smoothly and according to established guidelines.

All of the DanceSport technical officials exhibit unwavering loyalty and dedication to upholding the standards, integrity, and values of DanceSport. All of them prioritize their responsibilities, often going above and beyond to ensure the smooth running of competitions and events.

It is apparent that DanceSport technical officials exhibited a consistent level of professionalism across various demographic classifications, including gender, age, educational background, tenure, and role type. The absence of significant differences suggested a cohesive and uniform approach to professionalism within the DanceSport community in this region.

The DanceSport technical officials demonstrated a consistent level of administrative skills across various demographic categories, including gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work. The lack of significant differences highlighted a uniformity in the proficiency of administrative tasks among officials in the DanceSport community in this region.

The DanceSport technical officials exhibited a consistent level of commitment across various demographic categories, including gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and nature of work. The lack of significant differences underscored a unified dedication among officials toward their roles within the DanceSport community in this region.

The identified correlations highlight that as the level of professionalism increases, so do levels of administrative skills and commitment among these officials. This interconnectedness showed the holistic nature of their roles, where professionalism influences their ability to effectively manage administrative tasks and maintain high levels of commitment to their responsibilities within the DanceSport community.

The following recommendations were based on the foregoing findings and the conclusions made by the researcher:

The Department of Education (DepEd) may continue to invest in robust training and professional development programs that specifically target DanceSport technical officials regardless of demographic factors, fostering a unified standard of professionalism.

School heads are encouraged to implement strategies to recognize and reward professionalism consistently among DanceSport technical officials, and foster an environment that values meritocracy and supports continuous improvement in professionalism, administrative and organizational skills, and commitment.

Coaches can integrate ethical and professional conduct into DanceSport coaching programs, focusing on enhancing professionalism, and administrative skills fostering commitment to roles, and equipping athletes with an understanding of event logistics, rules, and protocol.

DanceSport technical officials are encouraged to take the initiative in participating in continuous professional development activities to enhance professionalism, strengthen administrative skills, and deepen commitment to upholding competence in DanceSport events.

Learners are suggested to embrace diversity and inclusion within the DanceSport community, respecting all officials regardless of their background and they may engage actively in training and competitions to uphold the integrity and standards of the sport.

Stakeholders are encouraged to support initiatives that promote diversity and inclusion within DanceSport, including policies that recognize the contributions of LGBTQ+ officials and those from diverse age groups.

Researcher maybe motivated to investigate innovative approaches and best practices that enhance professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment among technical officials.

Future Researchers are encouraged to conduct qualitative inquiries into the underlying factors influencing professionalism, administrative skills, and commitment among DanceSport technical officials. They may focus on developing evidence-based recommendations for improving career satisfaction and inclusivity within the DanceSport community.

References

- American Psychological Association. (2013). Ethical principles of psychologists and code of conduct. *American Psychologist*, 68(9)
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99-120.
- Baron, R. M., and Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173-1182.
- Bhat, A. (2023). Descriptive correlational: Descriptive vs correlational research. QuestionPro.
- Bongabong, L. (2022). Pampering descriptive-correlational research design.
- Brown, J. (2019). The Role of Judges in DanceSport Competitions. *Journal of Sports Ethics*, 15(3), 230-245.
- Bryman, A., and Bell, E. (2019). *Business research methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Chelladurai, P. (2001). *Managing organizations for sport and physical activity*. Scottsdale, AZ: Holcomb Hathaway.
- Cialdini, R. B. (1984). *Influence: The psychology of persuasion*. New York: HarperCollins.
- Cunningham, G. B., and Sagas, M. (2002). The role of gender in the employment of intercollegiate coaches: Implications for Title IX of the Education Amendments of 1972. *Gender Roles. Journal of Management* 47(3-4)
- Cook, A., and Matthew, G. (2017). Resilience in sports officiating. *Journal of Applied Sports Psychology*, 29(4), 410-425.
- Davis, M., Johnson, R., and Smith, K. (2015). Ethical conduct among sports officials. *Journal of Sports Ethics*, 20(1), 42-59.
- Devi, B., Lepcha, N, and Basnet, S. (2023). Application Of Correlational Research Design In Nursing And Medical Research. Xi'an Shiyu Daxue Xuebao (Ziran Kexue Ban)/Journal of Xi'an Shiyu University. 65. 60-69.
- Drucker, P. F. (2005). *Management: Tasks, responsibilities, practices*. New York: HarperCollins.
- Essel, H. B., Vlachopoulos, D., Tachie-Menson, A., Nunoo, F. K. N., and Johnson, E. E. (2022, April 4). Nomophobia Among Preservice Teachers: A Descriptive Correlational Study At Ghanaian Colleges Of Education.
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Lang, A. G., and Buchner, A. (2007). Gpower 3: A flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behavior Research Methods*, 39(2), 175-191.
- Freidson, E. (2001). *Professionalism: The third logic*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fort, R. D., and Fizek, J. (2004). *International sports economics comparisons*. Westport, CT: Praeger.
- Garcia, L. (2019). Regional Differences in DanceSport: A Comparative Analysis. *Sports Management Review*, 22(4), 480-494.
- Garcia, M., and Hernandez, L. (2020). Enhancing Commitment of DanceSport Technical Officials: The Impact of Professional Development Programs. *Journal of Professional Training*, 16(3)
- Garcia, M., and Lopez, R. (2019). Enhancing Professionalism in DanceSport Technical Officials: The Impact of Training Programs. *Journal of Professional Training*, 15(2), 87-105
- Gomez, L., and Hernandez, M. (2018). Enhancing Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials: The Impact of Training Programs. *Journal of Professional Training*, 20(3), 145-162
- Gravetter, F. J., and Forzano, L. B. (2020). *Research methods for the behavioral sciences*. Cengage Learning.
- Hawkins, M., Elsworth, G.R., Nolte, S., and Osborne, R.H. Validity Arguments For Patient-Reported Outcomes: Justifying The Intended Interpretation And Use Of Data. *J Patient Rep Outcomes* 5, 64
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., and Snyderman, B. B. (1959). *The motivation to work*. New York: John Wiley and Sons.
- Holmes, J., and Brown, M. (2019). The role of technology in sports officiating: Implications for DanceSport technical officials. *Journal of Sports Officiating*, 10(1), 32-48.

- Homans, G., and Blau, P. (1964). The Social Exchange Theory. *American Journal of Sociology*, 70(5), 598-606.
- Johnson, T. (2015). Understanding Professionalism in a Modern Context. *Journal of Occupational Studies*, 10(1), 15-29.
- Jones, C., Brown, D., and Lee, E. (2020). Emotional and mental commitment of DanceSport technical officials. *International Journal of Sports Officiating*, 8(3), 45-60.
- Lee, H. (2017). Leadership and administrative skills in sports. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 12(1), 56-64.
- Martinez, R. (2017). Assessing Administrative Skills of DanceSport Technical Officials: A Comparative Study. *Journal of Dance Administration*, 36(2), 75-92.
- Martinez, R., and Lopez, A. (2019). Assessing Commitment Levels of DanceSport Technical Officials: A Comparative Study. *Journal of Dance Research*, 45(4), 210-225.
- Masten, A. S. (2021). Ordinary magic: Resilience processes in development. *American Psychologist*, 56(3), 227-238.
- Meyer, J. P., and Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human resource management review*,
- Parent, M. M., and Slack, T. (2006). *International perspectives on the management of sport*. Burlington, MA: Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Roberts, L. (2020). *Administrative Skills in Sports Management: A Practical Guide*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Ogers, T., and Carter, S. (2016). Commitment among sports officials. *Journal of Sports Psychology*
- Seligman, M. E. P. (2002). Positive psychology, positive prevention, and positive therapy. In C. R. Snyder and S. J. Lopez (Eds.), *Handbook of Positive Psychology* (pp. 3-12). Oxford University Press.
- Shaughnessy, J. J., Zechmeister, E. B., and Zechmeister, J. S. (2019). *Research methods in psychology*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Smith, R. (2018). The evolving role of DanceSport technical officials in the digital age. *Journal of Sports Technology*, 12(4), 211-226.
- Smith, J., and Johnson, A. (2018). Assessing Professionalism in DanceSport Technical Officials: A Comparative Study. *Journal of Dance Research*,
- Smith, J., and Doe, M. (2018). Professionalism in sports officiating: A comparative study. *Journal of Professional Training*, 32(2), 123-139.
- Smith, R. (2018). The Backbone of DanceSport: An Examination of Officials in Competitive Dance. *Dance Research Journal*, 20(2), 68-82.
- Thompson, S., and Evans, M. (2020). Administrative skills in sports officiating. *Journal of Professional Training*, 55(4), 309-322.
- Vasquez, J., and Peralta, R. (2015). Examining the Impact of Professional Training on the Commitment Levels of Sports Officials in Local Events. *Journal of Sports Management*
- Wang, S. (2016). The Role of Commitment in Professional Sports: A Case Study. *Journal of Sports Management and Research*, 7(1), 42-59.
- Vroom, V. H. (1964). *Work and Motivation*. New York: Wiley.
- Williams, R. (2017). Effective Time Management in Athletic Competitions. *Journal of Sports Logistics*, 5(2), 120-134.
- Williams, L., Johnson, A., and Smith, J. (2019). The impact of training on professionalism among sports officials. *Journal of Professional Training*, 47(3), 22-37.
- Williams, R., and Smith, R. (2019). The dedication and responsibilities of DanceSport technical officials. *Journal of DanceSport Officiating*, 5(2), 87-102.
- Wilson, K., Chen, L., and Brown, M. (2021). Factors affecting commitment in sports officiating. *Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 45(2), 200-215.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rosebelle S. Baldostamon
Bungsuan National High School
Department of Education – Philippines